

1 **An E2F stabilizing ncRNA, EMSLR, functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of an
9 E2F stabilizing ncRNA, EMSLR, with functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Priyanka, P., Sharma, M., Das, S. and Saxena, S., 2022. E2F1-induced lncRNA, EMSLR
12 regulates lncRNA LncPRESS1. Scientific reports, 12(1), p.2548.
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